

Management

THE EFFECT OF MARKETING STRATEGY, COMMUNITY PERCEPTION, AND COMMUNITY SATISFACTION ON THE MAKING DECISION TO CHOOSE PRIVATE MADRASAH TSANAWIYAH IN JAMBI PROVINCE

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Abstract

Decision making is the choice of certain behavioral (behavioral) alternatives from two or more alternatives that exist to determine the direction of the objectives to be achieved. Decision making to choose a madrasa is a very strategic decision to determine the future of the school. So it is necessary to examine the factors that influence the decision to choose a madrasa. This study aims to examine the effect of marketing strategies, community perceptions and community satisfaction on the decision to choose Private Madrasah Tsanawiyah in Jambi Province both partially and simultaneously, also directly and indirectly.

This research is a quantitative study with a survey method carried out on Private Madrasah Tsanawiyah in Jambi Province. The population in this study amounted to 178 people who send their children to Private Madrasah Tsanawiyah. Analytical tools with interpreted Path Analysis with Determination Analysis (R Square), Hypothesis Test with t test and f test, and alpha 5 percent. The results showed that: 1) the marketing strategy had an effect on community satisfaction with a value of 2,130; 2) community perceptions affect community satisfaction with a value of 6.196. 3) marketing strategies and community perceptions of community satisfaction. With a calculated F value of 89.549; 4) marketing strategy towards the decision to choose madrasah with a value of t count of 5.136; 5) community perceptions of the decision to choose madrasah with a score of 6.467; 6) marketing strategies and community perceptions of the decision to choose a madrasah with an Fcount of 169,691; 7) community satisfaction with the decision to choose a madrasah with a tcount of 13,529; 8) marketing strategies, community perceptions, and community satisfaction with the decision to choose madrasah with a tcount of 134.807; 9) marketing strategies towards the decision to choose madrasah through community satisfaction. With tcount of 5.681; and 10) community perceptions of the decision to choose a madrasah through community satisfaction with an Fcount of 5.168.

Based on these findings, the better the madrasah marketing strategy, community perceptions, community satisfaction, the more the community will make the decision to choose madrasahs.

Keywords: Marketing Strategy; Community Perception and Community Satisfaction and Decision to Choose.

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1. Introduction

Background

The existence of management in an institution is a very important thing. Because in management it covers all aspects of management and regulation in an institution, what else is an educational institution in which there are many people. Educational institutions such as madrasa education institutions are a formal institution that is very strategic to develop thinking (science), opinion and most importantly is to be able to develop and improve human resources (students' resources) themselves optimally. Madrasah educational institutions also consist of a collection of intelligent people, such as principals, education personnel (Teachers), educational staff (administrators), students (students) and even to the madrasa guard (security). All of them are united to build their institutions into a professional, advanced and developing educational institution (madrasah).

Developing educational institutions is one of the main tasks and responsibilities of the head of the madrasa as a manager. The task must be carried out optimally, planned and directed by the head of the madrasa and by the educational staff in the madrasa. Because if the educational institution develops, advances and is well-known, then the madrasa will be glimpsed and sought after by many people. And of course, it will affect the in-put madrasa. A large number of inputs is one indicator that the madrasa is progressing and developing. The development of educational institutions is also inseparable from the role of the principal and the management of madrasah relations with the community.

Madrasah and communities have a very close relationship in achieving the goals of madrasahs or education effectively and efficiently. The head of the madrasa must also be able to utilize the human resources available in the madrasa, and how to make the madrasa students have achievements (prestige) that can boast and make the name of the madrasa proud, both at local, national and international levels, so that the madrasa becomes target and even become a choice for the community, and then in the end the community or parents decide their choice on the Private Tsanawiyah Madrasah.

Decision making in choosing a madrasa is not an easy matter. Decision making is a very hard job. Because if it is wrong to make a decision to choose, it will affect someone. What's more, choosing madrasahs / madrasahs that will entrust their children for three years with a myriad of hopes. According to George R Terry, decision making is to choose alternatives from two or several existing alternatives to determine the direction of the goals to be achieved. These alternatives can be in the form of a physical condition, or creative endeavors, or a place to gather thoughts, feelings, creative endeavors or a place to gather thoughts, feelings and knowledge to carry out an action.

The results of the interview mentioned above can be seen that decision making in choosing schools is very dependent and very determined by their parents. As parents, of course they want their

children to go to schools / madrasas which they think have more value than other schools or madrasas. Therefore, madrasas as institutions of Islamic education, must have more value than madrasas or other schools so that the community will look at them. The community has been very smart in choosing and deciding where their children will go to school. In fact, not a few parents are able to find information relating to the madrasa or the school to be visited. Especially in the current era, where there are no more boundaries between one another in accessing information about madrasas or schools.

In today's modern era, and along with the progress and development of science and technology, and the intense competition between educational institutions (madrasas), most educational institutions in Indonesia have changed functions. Initially educational institutions were only made pure as a learning process and not even imagined in the least that in madrasas or schools there are economic and business (investment education) elements. According to Imam Machalli, education is not merely a service, but also contains an economic perspective of education which is an investment item that is not just economic growth. In the praxis of modern education management, one of the five functions of education is the technical-economic function both at the individual level to the global level. Because of the economic, business element in educational institutions, both public and private, it is necessary to have marketing in an educational institution that is increasingly developing and advancing.

According to Alma, that ordinary people don't know much about marketing (marketing), many people feel surprised, shocked and even confused about the term marketing education. Because talking about marketing, people are more focused on economic problems. Most people think that the educational institution will be commercialized. Even though it is not the same and not congruent between marketing and commercial, although both terms are familiarly used in the business field. Business activities can be carried out in two sectors, namely sectors that seek or profit, and sectors that do not pursue profits. Likewise, the term marketing, there is marketing in a "profit organization" and there is marketing in "nonprofit organizations".

Instead the madrasa receives a source of funds from donors or parent institutions that do not expect anything in return from the madrasa. From the budget obtained. Madrasas produce educational services that will be offered to their customers (students). In contrast to companies, if the education services produced by the madrasa are not in accordance with the needs and desires of their students, donors may still be giving more funds, if they still consider the madrasa. Conversely, although the education services produced by the madrasa are in accordance with the needs and desires of their students, this does not necessarily guarantee that the funds and donors will increase for madrasah. Thus, educational institutions that refer to the economic (business) level are things that cannot be reversed again. Therefore, educational institutions must be prepared to face competition and global competition, which covers all aspects, such as aspects of quality, quality, both teacher quality and quality of students, extracurricular activities, all of which will affect aspects of student (student) recruitment. According to Imam Machalli, competition in the world of education is inevitable, many educational institutions are abandoned by their customers, so many mergers occur from several educational institutions.

The ability of administrators to understand marketing education is a prerequisite in maintaining and increasing the growth of their institutions. The head of the madrasa must also be able to utilize

the human resources available in the madrasa, and how to make the madrasa students have achievements (prestige) that can boast and make the name of the madrasa proud, both at local, national and international levels, so that the madrasa becomes target and even become a choice for the community, and then in the end the community or parents decide their choice on the Private Tsanawiyah Madrasah.

Decision making in choosing a madrasa is not an easy matter. Decision making is a very hard job. Because if it is wrong to make a decision to choose, it will affect someone. What's more, choosing madrasah that will entrust their children for three years with a myriad of hopes. According to George R Terry, decision making is to choose alternatives from two or several existing alternatives to determine the direction of the goals to be achieved. These alternatives can be in the form of a physical condition, or creative endeavors, or a place to gather thoughts, feelings, creative endeavors or a place to gather thoughts, feelings and knowledge to carry out an action.

Decision making in choosing madrasahs is indeed very dependent on children and their parents. Decision making in choosing a madrasah at this time cannot be decided by the child alone, but it cannot be separated from the peran interfering with his parents. Because parents usually better understand which school to choose for their child. of course, parents will choose a quality school, the best and the best. This was expressed by one of the students who said that it was very decisive for me to go to school where my parents were, I was told by parents to go to school A, but not to graduate, and to go back to school B nor graduate and finally I enter this madrasa. Whereas the other children also said that the decision I would go to school was determined by my parents, I could not do anything, everything was decided by my parents where I would go to school.

In today's modern era, and along with the progress and development of science and technology, and the intense competition between educational institutions (madrasahs), most educational institutions in Indonesia have changed functions. Initially educational institutions were only made pure as a learning process and not even imagined in the least that in madrasahs or schools there are economic and business (investment education) elements. According to Imam Machalli, education is not merely a service, but also contains an economic perspective of education which is an investment item that is not just economic growth. In the praxis of modern education management, one of the five functions of education are the technical-economic function both at the individual level to the global level. Because of the economic, business element in educational institutions, both public and private, it is necessary to have marketing in an educational institution that is increasingly developing and advancing.

According to David Wijaya, marketing to profit-oriented organizations (companies) with non-profit organizations in madrasahs is very different. The difference lies in the way the two organizations obtain the resources needed to carry out their operations. The company obtains the first capital from investors or shareholders. If the company has operated, the company's operational funds are mainly obtained from the sale of the company's goods or services. in this case the company only faces one important element, namely the customer. If the goods or services produced by the company can satisfy customers, business transactions will occur so that the company has funds to continue its operations.

Madrasah obtain funding from donors or parent institutions that do not expect anything in return from the madrasa. From the budget obtained. Madrasahs produce educational services that will be offered to their customers (students). In contrast to companies, if the education services produced by the madrasa are not in accordance with the needs and desires of their students, donors may still be giving more funds, if they still consider the madrasa. Conversely, although the education services produced by the madrasa are in accordance with the needs and desires of their students, this does not necessarily guarantee that the funds and donors will increase for madrasah. To see the decision-making of Private Islamic Primary Schools in the Jambi Province, an initial survey is needed. This initial survey was carried out on parents who send their children to private Madrasahs in Jambi City, Bungo District and Tanjung Jabung Barat District. The survey results can be seen in the following table:

Table 1: Preliminary Survey Results Data on Decision Making Variables in Jambi City

No	Indikator	Skala Penilaian					Persentas
		SS	S	RG	TS	STS	
1	Pengetahuan	15	41	18	10	16	100%
2	Sikap	17	45	10	8	18	100%
3	Kepribadian	20	40	12	10	18	100%
4	Gaya Hidup	18	43	8	15	16	100%
5	Demografi	21	40	10	12	17	100%

Based on table 1 it can be concluded that of the five indicators of decision-making variables: 1). Knowledge of 15% strongly agreed, 41% agreed, 18% hesitated, 10% disagreed and 16% strongly disagreed, 2). Attitudes, 17% strongly agree, 45% agree, 10% doubt, 8% disagree and 18% strongly disagree, 3). Personality 20% strongly agree, 40% agree, 12% doubt, 10% disagree and 18% strongly disagree, 4). Lifestyle 18% strongly agreed, 43% agreed, 8% hesitated, 15% disagreed, and 16% strongly disagreed, 5). Demographics 21% strongly agree, 40% agree, 10% doubt, 12% disagree and 17% strongly disagree. The variables above show that all indicators on the decision-making variable still strongly influence the decision making of madrasah.

Table 2: Preliminary Survey Results Data on Decision Making Variables in the Bungo Region

No	Indikator	Skala Penilaian					Persentas
		SS	S	RG	TS	STS	
1	Pengetahuan	15	38	21	12	14	100%
2	Sikap	19	42	13	9	12	100%
3	Kepribadian	17	40	15	11	17	100%
4	Gaya Hidup	18	44	10	12	16	100%
5	Demografi	22	39	11	10	18	100%

Based on table 2 it can be concluded that of the five indicators of decision-making variables: 1). Knowledge of 15% strongly agreed, 38% agreed, 21% hesitated, 12% disagreed and 14% strongly disagreed, 2). Attitudes, 19% strongly agree, 42% agree, 13% doubt, 9% disagree and 12% strongly disagree, 3). Personality 17% strongly agree, 40% agree, 15% doubt, 11% disagree and 17% strongly disagree, 4). Lifestyle 18% strongly agree, 44% agree, 10% doubt, 12% disagree, and 16% strongly disagree, 5). Demographics 22% strongly agree, 39% agree, 11% doubt, 10%

disagree and 18% strongly disagree. The variables above show that all indicators on the decision-making variable still strongly influence the decision making of madrasah.

Table 3: Preliminary Survey Results Data on Decision Making Variables in the Kuala Tungkal

No	Indikator	Skala Penilaian					Persentas
		SS	S	RG	TS	STS	
1	Pengetahuan	16	42	17	10	18	100%
2	Sikap	18	44	13	9	16	100%
3	Kepribadian	21	39	12	13	17	100%
4	Gaya Hidup	18	43	8	15	16	100%
5	Demografi	22	41	7	12	18	100%

Based on table 3 it can be concluded that of the five indicators of decision-making variables: 1). Knowledge 16% strongly agree, 42% agree, 17% doubtful, 10% disagree and 18% strongly disagree, 2). Attitude, 18% strongly agree, 44% agree, 12% doubt, 9% disagree and 16% strongly disagree, 3). Personality 21% strongly agree, 39% agree, 12% doubt, 13% disagree and 17% strongly disagree, 4). Lifestyle 18% strongly agreed, 43% agreed, 8% hesitated, 15% disagreed, and 16% strongly disagreed, 5). Demographics 22% strongly agree, 41% agree, 7% doubt, 12% disagree and 18% strongly disagree. The variables above show that all indicators on the decision-making variable still strongly influence the decision making of madrasah.

Based on a preliminary survey conducted in Jambi City Private Madrasah Tsanawiyah, Tsanawiyah Madrasah in Bungo District and in Kuala Tungkal Private Tsunami Education, it was shown that decision making in choosing Private Tsunami Education was strongly influenced by knowledge, attitudes, personality, lifestyle and demography. This can be seen in table 1, table 2 and table 3 which states that most (above 20%) respondents answered strongly agree and agreed to the indicators on the decision-making variable.

2. Theoretical Basis

2.1. Decision Making

Decisions are the result of solutions in a problem that must be dealt with firmly by anyone and wherever they are. In the Big Dictionary of Science, Decision Making is defined as the selection of decisions or policies based on certain criteria. This process includes two or more alternatives because if there is only one alternative there will not be one decision to be taken.¹ According to J.Reason Decision making can be considered as a result or output of mental or cognitive processes that lead to the selection of a course of action among several alternatives available.

According to George R. Terry decision making is the selection of certain behavioral alternatives (behaviors) from two or more alternatives that exist to determine the direction of the goals to be achieved. Then the alternative can be a physical condition, or creative endeavors, or a place to gather thoughts, feelings and knowledge to carry out an action.

According to Siswanto, decision making is a series of activities carried out by someone in an effort to solve the problems being faced, then determine various alternatives that are considered the most

rational and in accordance with the organization's environment. So making a decision means choosing and setting one alternative that is considered to be the most profitable of several alternatives faced.

According to Herbert A. Simon in Siswanto proposed a useful model as a basis in the decision-making process, namely: 1). Research, namely studying the environment on conditions that require decisions, raw data obtained, processed and tested to be used as a direction of action that can identify the problem, 2). Design, which is registering, developing and analyzing the direction of possible actions. This activity includes the process of understanding the problem, producing solutions, and testing the feasibility of the solution, 3). Election, namely determining the direction of a particular action from the whole, the choice is determined and implemented.

2.2. Educational Services Marketing Strategy

According to Lockhart in Wijaya, marketing education services is a way to do something where students, parents, school employees and the public consider the school as a community support institution that is dedicated to serving the needs of customers of educational services. Whereas Kotler and Fox in Wijaya, put forward marketing definitions used specifically for schools as carefully formulated analysis, planning, implementation, and control programs designed to produce voluntary exchange of value with target markets / target markets (target marketing) services education to achieve school goals.

Then Kotler and Fox, define the main purpose of marketing education services, namely to: 1). fulfill the school's mission with a large success rate, 2). Increase customer satisfaction in education services, 3). Increase interest in educational resources and 4). Increase efficiency in the activities of marketers of education services. Schools need a marketing strategy for education services because schools are a service sector that requires a special marketing orientation, so that it can be further identified Gray in Wijaya explains five important stages in implementing marketing education services, namely: 1). Identify the needs or problems of marketing education services, 2). Conduct research or marketing audits of education services, 3). Conduct marketing planning for education services, 4). Determine the marketing mix of education services and 5). Determine the strategies and tactics of marketing education services.

According to Lockhar in Wijaya, there are five wrong concepts about marketing education services. This concept can damage the marketing business of education services and waste school resources, these five concepts are: 1). Marketing education services is a special activity. Marketing education services is not an initial school effort to overcome the education crisis, then the concept was abandoned when the education crisis had ended. However, marketing education services must be a business that is constantly attached to daily school activities and inherent in the mindset of all school employees. 2). Marketing education services is an unwelcome activity. Marketing education services are usually disliked by customers of educational services because they do not cooperate with educating students. However, we need to observe that private universities, institutions, academies and schools have marketed themselves successfully. They consider the education service marketing program important because it can create schools that are able to survive in the midst of intense educational competition. If we make an education improvement program to improve the learning environment, the interest in the school's physical environment.

Or public relations, we already think in the same way as education service marketers who are developing marketing services for educational services. 3). marketing education services is one difficult task. Marketers of education services often complain because they spend a lot of time marketing marketing services. The marketing activities of educational services require time and effort, but the reward for marketing successful educational services is a valuable educational investment. 4). Effective education services programs can reduce the time marketers of educational services to connect with parents of dissatisfied students, recruit donors and school employees, find additional resources and build community support. 5) Marketing of education services is a sales activity. many people think marketing and sales are the same, even though the two definitions are different. Marketing activities are strategic, comprehensive, and indirect.

2.3. Community Perception

Perception in the process is influenced by several factors that make the process of perception grow. According to Sarlito W Sarwono that differences in perception can be caused by things as follows:

- Attention, usually we do not win all the stimuli around us at once, but we focus our attention on an object or two objects only. The difference in focus between one person and another, causes differences in perception between them.
- Sets. Set is someone's hope for stimuli that will arise. For example, on a runner who is ready on the "star" line, there is a set that will sound a gun when he has to start running, difference sets can cause different perceptions.
- Needs. Momentary needs as well as those that are settled on someone, that person will influence perception. Thus, different needs will also cause different perceptions.
- Value system. The value system that applies in a society also influences perception. An experiment in the United States (Bruner and Godman, 1947, Carter and Schooler, 1949) showed that children from poor families perceive coins as larger than the actual size. This symptom was not found in children who came from rich families.
- Personality traits. Characteristics of personality will also influence perceptions such as two people who work in the same office are under the supervisor of the boss, people who are shy and people who have high self-confidence will be different in perceiving their superiors.

2.4. Community Satisfaction

Consumer satisfaction can be shown through consumer attitudes after consuming the products obtained. Customer satisfaction will be seen from how well the product is obtained and felt. The better the quality of the product obtained, the better customer satisfaction will be. The word satisfaction (satisfaction) according to Fandy Tjiptono and Gregorius Chandra (2005: 195) comes from the Latin "satis" which means that it is quite good, adequate, and "factio" which means doing or making. Satisfaction can be interpreted as "an effort to fulfill something" or "make something adequate". The following is the understanding of customer satisfaction according to several experts, including: According to Nasution M. N, "Customer satisfaction is a condition where the needs, desires, and expectations of customers can be fulfilled through the products consumed". Based on the understanding of customer satisfaction, it can be concluded that customer satisfaction is the level of one's feelings after consuming a product or service to the needs, desires, and

expectations he wants. According to Lupiodi, in determining the level of satisfaction there are five factors that must be considered by public service organizations, namely:

- Quality of products / services, the public will be satisfied if the results of their evaluation show that the products / services they use are of high quality.
- Quality of service, the public will feel satisfied if they get good or appropriate service.
- Emotional, the public will feel proud and get confidence that other people will be amazed by it when using products / services with certain brands that tend to have a higher level of satisfaction.
- Prices, products that have the same quality but have lower prices will give a higher value.
- Costs, the public does not need to incur additional costs to not need to waste time getting the desired goods or services.

3. Framework of Thinking

Departing from the theory and research, the framework used by researchers in this study is described as follows:

Picture 1:

The thinking framework tries to analyze the effect of marketing strategies on community satisfaction, marketing strategies on decision making, community perceptions of decision making, marketing strategies and public perceptions of decision making, marketing strategies and community satisfaction with decision making, community perceptions and marketing strategies, perceptions community, and community satisfaction with decision making.

4. Research Hypothesis

From the exposure of the theoretical foundation used and the framework of the above, the research hypothesis can be drawn as follows:

- 1) Community perception has a direct effect on community satisfaction
- 2) Marketing Strategy and Public Perception directly influence Community Satisfaction.
- 3) Marketing Strategy has a direct effect on Madrasah Decision Making

- 4) Community Perceptions Directly Influence Madrasah Decision Making
- 5) Marketing Strategy and Perception of Influential Communities directly on Madrasah Decision Making.
- 6) Satisfaction of Influential Communities directly with Madrasah Decision Making
- 7) Marketing Strategy, Community Perception, and Community Satisfaction Direct Effects on Madrasah Decision Making
- 8) Direct Marketing Strategy Influence on Madrasah Decision Making Through Community Satisfaction.
- 9) Marketing Strategies Direct Effect on Madrasah Decision Making Through Community Satisfaction.
- 10) Direct Perception of Influence on Madrasah Decision Making Through Community Satisfaction.

5. Research Methodology

This research was carried out by using a quantitative approach with survey methods and using path analysis and regression techniques (path analysis) that would test the direct and indirect effects on each research variable. The object of the research was in formal education institutions, namely in Private Islamic Madrasahs in Jambi provinces, namely Bungo District, Jambi City, and Tanjung Jabung Barat District. In this study four variables were discussed, namely Marketing Strategy (X1), Community Perception (X2), Community Satisfaction (X3), and decision to choose (X4). The constellation of influences between these variables can be seen in the following models:

Picture 2:

Information:

x_1 = Marketing strategy

x_2 = Community Perception

x_3 = Community Satisfaction

x_4 = Decision-making

ϵ = other influencing factors that appear in the study

6. Population and Samples

Creswell defines the population as a group of individuals who share the same characteristics (a population is a group of individuals who have the same characteristic) and a sample is a subgroup of the target population planned to be studied (a sample is a subgroup of the target population that the researchers plan to study for generalizing about the target population).

The population in this study is the people who send their children to private Madrasahs in Jambi Province, with areas in the West Tanjung Jabung District, Jambi City, and Bungo District. If specified in the region, the number of Private Islamic Primary Schools in Tanjung Jabung Barat Regency is 46 madrasahs, 35 Private Islamic Madrasahs in Jambi City, and 43 Private Islamic Madrasahs in Bungo District. In detail, can be seen in the following table:

Table 4: Total Madrasah Tsanawiyah

No	Kab/Kota	Tsanawiyah		Total
		Negeri	Swasta	
1	Tanjung jabung Barat	3	43	46
2	Kota Jambi	6	29	35
3	Bungo	15	28	43
	Total	24	100	124

The overall population of the 3 study areas was 124 madrasahs. Where the population is the people who send their children to the madrasa especially class VII 2017-2018 school year with details as can be seen in the following table:

Table 5: Study Population

No	Region	School Total	Student Total
1	Tanjung Jabung Barat	45	645
2	Kota Jambi	35	538
3	Bungo	43	577
	Total	123	1760

From this population, only one private madrasa was taken in each Regency as a sample. For Jambi City, the Asas Islamiyah Sipin Madrasah Tsanawiyah was taken with consideration, geographically it is very strategically located on the edge of the Pattimura road, has B agriditation, is located in the middle of the village, and also includes Madrasahs that have long been established. For Tanjung Jabung Barat District, Hidayatul Islamiyah's Private Islamic Education Madrasah, better known as the MTs PHI, is considered to be very strategically located on the Kuala Tungkal City harbor road and also rehabilitated B, and PHI Madrasahs are classified as long-standing Madrasahs. with other Madrasahs. Whereas for the Bungo Regency region which is a Western region, the study was taken by Alfalah Private Madrasah, on the grounds that it was very strategically located on the Sumatran highway and also had agitation B. Consideration of time and costs was also the reason why only one madrasa was taken. The technique used in sampling was total sampling, because the sample did not reach 200 people. To see the size of the sample in this study can be seen in the table below:

Table 5: Study Sample

No	Region	School Total	Parent Student Total
1	Tanjung Jabung Barat	MTs. PHI	64
2	Kota Jambi	MTs. Asas Islamiyah	52
3	Bungo	MTs. Alfalah	62
	Jumlah		178

Of the 178 people, 30 samples were used to test the validity of the instrument. Whereas 148 is used to test research instruments. The sample consisted of 178 people, these were parents or guardians of students and students who sent their children to the Asas Islamiyah Sipin Madrasah Tsanawiyah Private City of Jambi, parents / guardians who sent their children to Alfalah Private Madrasa in the district of Bungo and parents / guardians who sent their children to the PHI Private Islamic School in Tanjung Jabung Barat District. The choice of parents / guardians of students is because the ones who determine their children want to go to school are their parents, parents better understand which schools are better among the good ones, children at the junior secondary level cannot guarantee the choice, because they are still in the child child. This is among the reasons why parents / guardians were used as samples in this study.

7. Research Result

Based on the analysis of data processing and discussion that has been described in the previous chapter, then some conclusions can be drawn in this study including:

- 1) Marketing strategies affect community satisfaction by calculating $t_{count} > t_{table}$ (2,130 > 1,655). This shows that the higher the marketing strategy of Madrasah Tsanawiyah, the higher the public interest in entering their children into the madrasa. Marketing strategies contribute significantly to community satisfaction. The coefficient of determination between the madrasah marketing strategy based on the results of this study can be concluded that the research hypothesis that states the marketing strategy influences people's satisfaction can be accepted. With this marketing strategy the madrasa should be even more active in socializing the madrasa. With an indication of a very significant marketing strategy it means that it can increase community satisfaction.
- 2) Community Perception influences Community Satisfaction by calculating $t_{count} > t_{table}$ (6,196 > 1,655). This shows that the higher the perspective of the community, the higher the satisfaction of the community. Community perceptions make a significant contribution to community satisfaction. Determination coefficient value between public perceptions Based on the results of this study, it can be concluded that the research hypothesis which states that public perceptions have an effect on community satisfaction can be accepted.
- 3) Marketing Strategy and Community Perception simultaneously influence the Community Satisfaction by calculating $F_{count} > F_{table}$ (89,549 > 3.06). This shows that the higher the marketing strategy, and simultaneous public perception, the higher the satisfaction of the community. Marketing strategies and public perceptions simultaneously contribute significantly to community satisfaction. The value of the determinant coefficient between marketing strategies and public perceptions simultaneously. Based on the results of this study it can be concluded that the research hypothesis which states marketing strategies and public perceptions simultaneously influences people's satisfaction can be accepted.

- 4) Marketing Strategy influences Decision Making Selecting the calculation of $t_{count} > t_{table}$ (5,136 > 1,655). This shows that the higher the madrasa marketing strategy, the higher the community will decide to choose a madrasa. The marketing strategy contributes significantly to the decision to choose. The value of the coefficient of determination between madrasah marketing strategies Based on the results of this study it can be concluded that the research hypothesis that states the marketing strategy influences the choice decision is acceptable.
- 5) Community Perception influences Decision Making Selecting the calculation of $t_{count} > t_{table}$ (4,467 > 1,655). This shows that the higher the public perception, the higher the decision to choose the madrasa. The marketing strategy contributes significantly to the decision to choose. The coefficient of determination between people's perceptions and the decision to choose. Based on the results of this study it can be concluded that the research hypothesis which states that public perceptions influence the decision to vote is acceptable.
- 6) Marketing strategies and public perceptions have an effect on decision making by calculating $F_{count} > F_{table}$ (169,691 > 3.06). This shows that the higher the marketing strategy and public perceptions, the higher the decision making in choosing madrasahs. Marketing strategies and public perceptions contribute significantly to the decision to choose. Determination coefficient value between madrasah marketing strategies. Based on the results of this study, it can be concluded that the research hypothesis which states marketing strategies and public perceptions influences decision making in choosing madrasahs is acceptable.
- 7) Satisfaction of the community has an effect on decision making choosing by calculating $t_{count} > t_{table}$ (13,529 > 1,655). In other words, the high and low decision-making decision is influenced by community satisfaction. This also means that if community satisfaction through the servants is given, the community will decide a lot to choose madrasahs to send their children to school. Based on the results of this study it can be concluded that the research hypothesis which states community satisfaction has an effect on decision making in choosing madrasah.
- 8) Marketing Strategy, Public Perception and community satisfaction together influence the decision making process by calculating $F_{count} > F_{table}$ (134,807 > 2.67). In other words the high and low decision making of choosing madrasahs by the community is able to be influenced by marketing strategies, public perceptions and community satisfaction. This also means that if the marketing strategy and public perception are carried out by the madrasah in socializing the madrasah, it will increase the willingness of the community to send their children to school in the madrasah. Based on the results of this study, it can be concluded that the research hypothesis that states marketing strategies and public perceptions simultaneously influences the decision making process is acceptable.
- 9) Marketing strategies can have a direct effect on choosing decision can also have an indirect effect that is from marketing strategies to community satisfaction (as an intervening variable) then to decision making to choose.
- 10) Community perceptions can have a direct effect on decision making and can also indirectly influence, from community satisfaction to marketing strategies (as intervening variables).

The theoretical model used in research is a model that has been developed and carried out by Kotler and Keller (2009) and Schiffman and Kanuk (2008). It was stated that in taking a decision, among others can be influenced by services, costs, location and reference groups.

Gambar 2. Model Penelitian
Sumber: Kotler dan Keller (2009); Schiffman dan Kanuk (2008)

The latest findings from this study can be seen in the influence of decision making that is seen not only partially and simultaneously, but also can be seen by using intervening variables and by using analysis paths (path analysis). The effect of the marketing strategy on decision making was tested using community satisfaction as its intervening variable. Likewise the influence of public perception on decision making with community satisfaction as an intervening variable. If it is described, the comparison will look as follows:

8. Conclusion

1) the marketing strategy had an effect on community satisfaction with a value of 2,130; 2) community perceptions affect community satisfaction with a value of 6.196. 3) marketing strategies and community perceptions of community satisfaction. With a calculated F value of 89.549; 4) marketing strategy towards the decision to choose madrasah with a value of t count of 5.136; 5) community perceptions of the decision to choose madrasah with a score of 6.467; 6) marketing strategies and community perceptions of the decision to choose a madrasah with an Fcount of 169,691; 7) community satisfaction with the decision to choose a madrasah with a tcount of 13,529; 8) marketing strategies, community perceptions, and community satisfaction with the

decision to choose madrasah with a tcount of 134.807; 9) marketing strategies towards the decision to choose madrasah through community satisfaction. With tcount of 5.681; and 10) community perceptions of the decision to choose a madrasah through community satisfaction with an Fcount of 5.168.

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